

LIBRARIANS' WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION: DO THEY MATTER ON THEIR JOB PERFORMANCE?

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ABSTRACT

Work-life balance has been a challenge since individuals began working from home during the pandemic without typical control over working hours or responsibilities. This study aimed to determine the work-life balance of librarians in terms of time balance and involvement balance, their job satisfaction and job performance. The research design used was a descriptive correlational design, participated in by 101 randomly sampled librarians in Northern Mindanao. The instrument used was a modified questionnaire made by the researcher based on the constructs used by Cabaraban& Borbon (2021) and Pulhin (2020), which is composed work-life balance questions, job satisfaction, and job performance. These instruments were distributed to the participants through their Emails and Facebook Messenger using the Google Forms. The statistical tools used were mean, frequency, and regression analysis. The findings of the study showed that librarians have a high work-life balance in terms of time and involvement. In terms of job satisfaction, the librarians are satisfied with their promotion, benefits, training and development, and working relationships with colleagues. In terms of job performance, the librarians view themselves as very good. The result of the regression analysis showed that work-life balance and job satisfaction significantly influence their job performance. This finding indicates that an increase in work-life balance and job satisfaction will increase job performance. It is recommended that library administrators conduct surveys of work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance at least every 3 years to determine the factors that can be improved to boost job performance.

Keywords: *Librarian, Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Job Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance (WLB) refers to the equilibrium between the demands of paid work and personal and family responsibilities (Hill et al., 2001). A healthy work-life balance is believed to contribute to employees' well-being (Joo & Lee, 2017). Job satisfaction happens when an employee feels he or she is having job stability, career growth, and a comfortable work-life balance. Job satisfaction is important because it can help a company understand how to motivate its employees to increase their productivity. Job performance is a set of workers' behaviors' that can be measured, monitored, and assessed as an achievement at the individual level. Job performance is of interest to the organization because of the importance of high productivity in the workplace (Ofoegbu & Joseph, 2013).

The global crisis caused by the Corona virus Disease (COVID-19) has significantly impacted jobs, workers, and the workplace. In light of the health risks posed by open offices, infectious disease threats like COVID-19 need to be recognized as part of the risks in the workplace.

In the Philippines, strict health protocols were implemented by the government to avoid the spread of the contagious disease from different offices. Cities and provinces were placed on lockdown. These restrictions prevented the libraries from opening. However, to ensure continuity and delivery of services, libraries from different sectors opted for alternative work arrangements in compliance with the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) and Civil Service Commission (CSC) guidelines, as well as those from the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) and Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). For government employees, CSC resolution No. 2000540 stated that "government agencies may adopt the following alternative work arrangements: work from home, skeleton workforce, four-day compressed work week, staggered working hours, and other alternative work arrangements." For private employees, DTI and DOLE interim guidelines on workplace prevention and control of COVID-19 state that employers may schedule alternative work arrangements such as shifts in working hours, and work-from-home arrangements wherever feasible and on a rotation basis.

This pressing situation posed by the COVID-19 pandemic puts the librarians in a difficult situation as the main purpose of the library is to provide quality and excellent services. With this, libraries need to be adaptable to make the necessary adjustments to anticipate and satisfy the demands of their patrons.

In this view, Work-Life Balance (WLB) has always been an issue in the said adjustments. Foremost, once individuals began to work out of their homes, they lost the customary degree of control over their working hours and the obligations placed on them at work (Thomas, 2021). The consequences of such imbalance may be poor satisfaction, mental stress, and unproductively, and problematic behavior at work or home, which may negatively affect work colleagues, family members, and the job performance of the employee. According to Abdirahman et al. (2020), these pressing issues of individuals in terms of human resource management should be addressed thoroughly by the

organizations. Regardless of their size, organizations should ensure that employees have adequate time to fulfill their family and work commitments.

Moreover, job satisfaction is another factor that may affect job performance. It is one of the most widely encountered research topics in organizational psychology (Inayat et al., 2021). Job satisfaction is the positive and enjoyable feeling that results from the evaluation of one's job or job experience (Locke, 1976). Job performance is the total expected value from employees' behaviors carried out over a predetermined period. It is related to how people perform in their professional obligations regarding the expected quantity and quality of their jobs.

Thus, the new normal has changed the working environment for librarians as well as how library services are delivered. This study aims to determine if these changes affect the librarians when it comes to their work-life balance and job satisfaction and whether these factors affect their performance at work. The researcher is interested in this study because few studies discuss the work-life balance and job satisfaction of librarians in the Philippines. Hence, there is a dearth of literature in this area because most of the studies are outside the Philippines and do not involve the workplace during the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, since COVID-19 has changed the workplace and might have an impact on employees' job performance, this study is pertinent to the current circumstances.

Framework

The researcher assumes that the participants' work-life balance and job satisfaction significantly influence their job performance. This supposition is based on Lewin's (1951) Person-Environment Fit Theory (P-E Fit), which examines the relationship between an individual's traits and their surroundings, noting how an individual influences their surroundings but also how the environment affects them (Holmbeck et al., 2009).

Accordingly, the Person-Environment Fit Theory states that there is a degree of match between individuals and some aspects of their work environment. The basic premise of this theory in research is that a particular environment is most compatible with the person's characteristics. This theory is related to the variables of work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance because the work environment of librarians has changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The theory states that there has to be a match between the employees' personalities and the work environment. Without this match, the employees cannot perform at their best, thereby, affecting their work environment balance, their job satisfaction, and their job performance.

The first independent variable in this study is the **work-life balance**. Work-life balance is defined by the Cambridge Dictionary (2021) as the ratio of time spent at work, time spent with family, and time spent on leisure activities. Work-life balance (WLB) is the balance between an employee's work and personal life, promoting an even balance. Kohll (2022) suggests that a healthy work-life balance promotes a healthy work atmosphere that prevents burnout, reduces stress, and thereby promotes a healthier work environment. The workplace and working conditions of an individual are likely to be attributed to their capacity to strike a balance between work and life. These include the

amount of flexibility, hours worked, the availability of sick and holiday leave, and the presence of support systems within the workplace. Offering employees these flexible work arrangements that enable them to engage in interests outside of work is imperative for their work-life balance.

Time balance and engagement/involvement balance are the main components that make up work-life balance. The first element is "*Time balance*," which refers to allocating the same amount of time to work and non-work roles. Time balance may also be defined in this study as the use of time proportionally to all the demands of the individual whether personal, at work, family, and others. Jenkins and Harvey (2019) commented that the shorter time boundaries make it challenging to balance professional and family life. Job demands negatively predicted WLB (Haar et al., 2019) as work hours consume a large portion of personal hours (Haar et al., 2019). This causes some important aspects of their lives to be depleted, undernourished, and ignored (Hughes et al., 2018). Thus, employees find less time for their "*quality*" family life (Jenkins and Harvey, 2019).

Further, Greenhaus and Colleagues (2014) also looked at the relationship between quality of life and work-family balance among public accounting professionals in the same study. Three elements invested substantial time in their combined work and family roles. Results showed that those who spent more time on family than work experienced a higher quality of life than those balanced individuals who spent more time at work than their family. To facilitate work-life balance, there is a need to deploy the WLB's supportive culture. Lamane-Harim et al. (2023) suggest that implementing a Work-Life Balance Supportive Culture (WLBSC) can enhance job satisfaction, organizational commitment, employee performance, and sustainability (e.g., Cuéllar-Molina et al., 2018).

Moreover, the second element of work-life balance is "*Involvement balance*," which denotes equal degrees of psychological involvement in both job and family roles. Involvement balance means the balancing of goals at work and family. Both of these factors are important in the work-life balance of the librarians. For instance, employees spend most of their time commuting (Denstadli et al., 2017) or meeting their work and family responsibilities. Dual dual-career couples in the nuclear family find it difficult to balance work and life without domestic help (Dumas and Perry-Smith, 2018; Srinivasan and SulurNachimuthu, 2022). Difficulty in a joint family is elderly care (Powell et al., 2019). Thus, family demands negatively predict WLB (Haar et al., 2019). However, spouse support enables better WLB (Dumas and Perry-Smith, 2018). Family support positively impacted WLB, especially for dual-career couples, with dependent responsibilities (Groysberg and Abrahams, 2014).

The second independent variable in this study is **job satisfaction**. Job satisfaction addresses a person's general attitude toward his or her job. This includes both positive and negative feelings toward the job. It also includes the sense of fulfilment and pride felt by people who do their daily tasks (Baughman et.al, 2013). Given the foregoing, job satisfaction also refers to the feelings and emotional aspects of an individual's experience towards his job as different from intellectual or rational aspects. It further refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job which acts as motivation to work.

In this study, job satisfaction is assessed considering the following dimensions: promotion, benefits, training and development, and relationship with colleagues. In terms of promotion, researchers contend that Quality of Work Life (QWL) is a favorable working environment that enhances satisfaction by providing employees with rewards, job safety and security, and career opportunities (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Sandhya, 2016). Samanta (2021) added that organization may regularly offer incentives and career promotions to increase librarians' level of interest.

Lacy and Copeland (2013) reported that librarians who participated in the mentoring program have acquired knowledge and skills on academic librarians, job opportunities, and professional expectations. Scholars such as Billett (2014) stressed that learning should be intentional and connected to work tasks, new skills, and employee's career goals. Billet also noted that access to learning is often contested in the workplace by social norms and structures such as seniority and task assignment (Thornton, 2021).

For benefits, past studies argued that when management provides benefits to employees, they tend to feel indebted to the organization and make more substantial efforts to ensure its well-being and goal attainment (Vayre, 2019). Corporate employers recognized that to remain competitive in a dual-career world they must offer some WLB incentives to attract highly qualified individuals. Some examples included extended vacation time, telecommuting, and parental leave (Townsend & Bugg, 2018). Thus, employee benefits were found to have a significant impact on job satisfaction (Tessima et al., 2013).

As for training and development, it is recommended that libraries develop and implement policies that support formal and informal training, and emphasize the links between updating and rewards (Chan & Auster, 2016). Similarly, academic librarianship must continuously innovate to remain relevant in stiff and very competitive colleges and universities with high technological advancements (Raju et al., 2017).

Finally, for relationships with colleagues, employees at both low and high status reported higher motivation when co-worker relationships were good (Ahmed, 2017). This implies that when employees find harmonious relations with their supervisors in the organization, they feel encouraged to do more work for the organization (Ahmed, 2017). In Nigeria, studies conducted by Ikonne and Onuoha (2015) and Ajayi and Abimbola (2013) found that good relationships among co-workers are more likely to result in higher levels of work satisfaction. These results imply that cordial and respectful relationships among co-workers enhance job satisfaction. It also indicates that managing good workplace relationships is a key contributing factor to increase job satisfaction and performance and productivity.

In an organizational behavior context, the social exchange theory is frequently used to explain the formation and maintenance of interpersonal relationships between employees and employers regarding reciprocation procedures (Rawshdeh et al., 2019). In a study conducted by Ikonne et al., (2015), it was revealed that factors such as job security, satisfactory relationship with supervisor, satisfactory interaction with colleagues, satisfactory interaction with information user/customer/clients, satisfactory job duties/job

schedules, satisfaction with the challenges of the job, task variety, and work autonomy, satisfactory communication climate in the workplace, and satisfactory job status/recognition at work are all significant conditions that elicit the achievement of job satisfaction among the librarians in the Federal and State Universities. The study also found that employees were not very satisfied with things like pay, working conditions, opportunities for research, managerial styles, and fringe benefits.

The dependent variable in this study is the **job performance**. Job performance is an assessment made by the company to assess their employee's job duties in terms of the expected quantity and quality of their jobs. Thevanes (2018) found that work-life balance has an impact on how well workers perform at work. When all else is equal, work-life balance enhances workers' job performance in a particular organization.

In the practices of WLB, family-supportive supervisor behaviors could play an important role, as these are expected to influence outcomes related to one's performance (Wang et al., 2013). In previous studies, supportive family supervisor behaviors were associated with job satisfaction and job performance (Heras et al., 2021). However, since the work-life balance supportive culture is a contextual factor and a new introduction into the working environment, it is expected to increase or decrease the extent of the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and job satisfaction and the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and job performance. It also raises the question of how moderation affects the existing relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and job satisfaction and the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and job performance. However, past studies have not investigated the moderating role of family-supportive supervisor behaviors (Lamane-Harim et al., 2021).

The entanglements between work and family are a significant source of psychological discomfort for employees (Lamane-Harim et al., 2021) as this could lead to job dissatisfaction and poor job performance, resulting to employee turnover and the intention to quit. On the other hand, Haar et al. (2014) stated that WLB has a positive impact on one's achievements, including performance.

The experience of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with an individual's work is the sequence of the extent of his positive or negative attitudes. A positive attitude towards the job is conceptually equivalent to job satisfaction and a negative attitude leads to dissatisfaction (Sirohi & Sharma). Inayat & Jahanzeb Khan (2021) averred that satisfied employees are better in performance and have a significant role in the uplifting of their organizations as compared to dissatisfied employees.

Several studies found evidence in the work-life balance literature that when organizations or supervisors care about their employees' personal and professional well-being, employees tend to reciprocate by helping them achieve their goals through improved performance (Campo et al., 2021). Therefore, based on the social exchange theory, this study argues that when organizations take care of the balance between employees' personal and professional lives, employees may increase their job satisfaction, and they are more inclined to reciprocate the favor through high job performance (Talukder et al., 2018). In such circumstances, the supervisor's formal and

informal support further increases employees perceived positive feelings toward the job and may strengthen the relationship between work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance. In support of the WLB and performance nexus, French et al. (2020) and Haar et al. (2014) opine that a high work-life balance also makes individuals to have higher job performance.

The foregoing discussions shaped the study's conceptualization. Figure 1 depicts the relationship of the variables identified in the study. The independent variables are work-life balance and job satisfaction, and the dependent variable is job performance.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram

Research Questions

This research aimed to identify the work-life balance and job satisfaction of librarians and its implication for their job performance in the new normal.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the librarian's work-life balance in terms of:
 - 1.1. Time Balance; and
 - 1.2. Involvement Balance
2. What is the participants' assessment of their job satisfaction in terms of:
 - 2.1 promotion;
 - 2.2 benefits;
 - 2.3 training and development;
 - 2.4 work relationship with colleagues
3. What is the participants' assessment of their job performance?
4. Do the participants' work-life balance and job satisfaction significantly influence their job performance?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design used in the study, followed by the details on how the participants were recruited, and how data were collected, managed, and analyzed.

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive correlational design refers to describing and examining relationships between variables without manipulating the variables (Cresswell, 2005). This method is appropriate for the study since it determined the librarians' work-life balance, job satisfaction, and its influence on their job performance.

Sampling was done using simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is selected for populations that are highly homogenous where the members of the research are randomly selected to participate in the research (Bhardwaj, 2019). In this study, the participants were the librarians in selected libraries in Northern Mindanao. A list of the librarians from Northern Mindanao was obtained from the Philippine Librarians Association Incorporated - Northern Mindanao Region Librarian Council (PLAI-NMRLC). The list contained 234 librarians. Out of these 234 librarians, 147 were taken as the actual participants of the study based on the calculation for the sample size of Taro Yamane. The 147 randomly selected participants were then sent and asked to answer the questionnaire in Google form online. The total number of participants who replied was one hundred one (101) and those who did not reply were forty-six (46). The libraries in Northern Mindanao were selected because of the proximity of the researcher.

The research instrument that was used for this study is a modified questionnaire designed by the researcher based on the constructs used by Cabaraban & Borbon (2021) which is also based on Pulhin (2020). The questionnaire was composed of four parts. These parts are discussed below.

The first part was composed of questions regarding the profile of the participants, including their: names (optional), age, gender, marital status, number of years as librarian, unit library assigned, and institution. The second part of the questionnaire was the Work-life balance questionnaire. It was composed of questions about the two components of work-life balance such as time balance and involvement balance. Specifically, time balance had nine questions, and Involvement balance also had nine questions. The third part of the questionnaire was the job satisfaction questionnaire. There were forty-three questions regarding job satisfaction. The fourth part was the job performance questionnaire. It was composed of 15 questions related to job performance.

Moreover, the first part, which is about the profiling of the participants, is composed of fill-in-the-blank questions, while the second to the fourth parts used a 5-point Likert scale with 1 being the lowest score and 5 being the highest.

The statistical tools that were used included the mean, frequency, and standard deviation to identify the librarian's work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance. For problem 4, regression analysis was used to determine the influence of work-life balance and job satisfaction on their job performance. Regression analysis is a way of mathematically sorting out which of those variables does indeed have an impact (Gallo, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the summary of the librarians' assessment of their work-life balance. Findings reveal that librarians generally have a "*high*" involvement balance as indicated by the overall mean of 3.91. This implies that librarians under study were able to balance equally their engagement with their family members by ensuring that they get to spend quality time with their spouse and children daily in times also of problems at the same time librarians were able to work on their tasks expected of them, and having a harmonious relationship with their immediate supervisor and colleagues.

In the same manner, librarians' understudy was able to provide equal time and manage well their work and life demands. This denotes that librarians can set boundaries with their work and family responsibilities. For instance, work-related tasks are done in the workplace during office hours and not bringing unfinished work at home. When they are at home, they focus on spending time with the family, doing household chores, and engaging in self-nurturing activities.

Table 1. Summary Table of Work-Life Balance

Components	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Time Balance	3.88	High	0.48
Involvement Balance	3.91	High	0.54
Overall	3.92	High	0.51

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' assessment of their job performance which refers to the criteria that assess whether a person performs a job well according to the job description. The data show that librarians rated their job performance "very good" as indicated by the overall mean of 4.41. This is the same rating given by fifty participants (50.50%). This demonstrates that librarians believe that they have necessary knowledge and skills both in professional and personal. This could be attributed to the professional development opportunities provided to them by their respective organizations, at the same time through their involvement in the webinars and seminars organized by various library associations and organizations that enabled them to be abreast of the latest trends in the field of librarianship. The librarian's performance is hinged on their level of job performance in the library (Nwokike & Udegbu, 2019). This can be regarded as a major contribution to the success of services in the library department of any university. The part of a librarian's job conduct that matters to the success of the library is their performance (Amusa et.al, 2013). Academic librarians are involved in the day-to-day management of the academic institutions' learning resources along with teaching, giving instructions to users, and carrying out daily administrative duties to ensure an encouraging learning and teaching environment (Nwokike & Udegbu, 2019).

Table 2. Summary of Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Job Performance

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Outstanding	45	44.6
3.51-4.50	Very Good	51	50.5
2.51-3.50	Good	5	4.95
1.51-2.50	Fair	0	0
1.00-1.50	Poor	0	0
	Total	101	100.0

Overall Mean	4.41
Interpretation	Very Good
SD	0.50

Table 3 presents the regression analysis of the influence of work-life balance and job satisfaction on their job performance. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=22.09$, $p = .000$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that participants who have high work-life balance and are more satisfied in their jobs also perform well.

Furthermore, 31.1 percent of the variability in their job performance can be accounted for by a combination of their work-life balance and job satisfaction. The remaining 68.9 percent can be attributed to other factors not covered in this study such as organizational justice, work engagement, and public service motivation (PSM) which may have direct effects on job performance. Transformational leadership (TFL) has been shown to affect employees' job performance (Ng, 2017).

Table 3. Summary of Regression Analysis of the Influence of Work-life Balance and Job Satisfaction on their Job Performance

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.916	.384		4.99	.000
Work-Life Balance	.292	.108	.269	2.71**	.008
Job Satisfaction	.340	.093	.365	3.68**	.000

Model Summary

$R = .557$ $R^2 = .311$ Adjusted $R^2 = .297$ $F = 22.09^{**}$ $p = .000$

**** significant at 0.01 level**

Considering the independent variables individually, findings show that job satisfaction came out as having the highest influence on their job performance, indicating that for every unit increase in their job satisfaction, there is a corresponding .340 increase in their job performance ($B=.340$, $t = 3.68$, $p = .000$). This is followed by work-life balance, indicating a corresponding .292 increase in their job performance for every unit increase

in their work-life balance ($B=.292$, $t = 2.71$, $p=.008$). Since the critical value is 0.01 and the absolute value of t is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis. This means that work life balance with a t value of 2.71 and job satisfaction with a t value of 3.68, influence the job performance of the participants.

Conclusions

Therefore, Work-life balance and Job satisfaction influence their job performance as assessed by the librarians of Northern Mindanao. This finding holds to the assertions of Lewin's Person-Environment Fit Theory (1951) that work-life balance and job satisfaction influence job performance, implying that librarians who have stabilized work demands and family demands are happier and more motivated at work. This finding further indicates that motivated employees who deliver satisfied library services to patrons will also ensure that patrons are satisfied with the services received.

Work-life balance is not an elusive dream but a sensible goal that contributes to overall well-being and satisfaction. By implementing strategies to prioritize both work and personal life, individuals can attain harmony, reduce stress, and lead fulfilling lives. Embracing work-life balance fosters productivity, strengthens relationships, and promotes a healthier lifestyle, in the end enhancing the quality of life for individuals and their loved ones. As librarians continue to thrive and navigate the demands of the modern world, it is essential that achieving balance is not a luxury but a necessity for a happy and fulfilling life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. That library administrator may conduct, at least every 3 years, surveys on the librarians' work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance to determine areas that need potential improvement. Improving the conditions of these factors may result in increased job performance.
2. That librarians may consider undertaking a course or training project management to ensure that programs and activities are implemented as scheduled.
3. Future researchers may conduct other methods of research like qualitative methods and mixed methods to triangulate the results of this research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher sought the approval of the school's Research Ethics Committee to ensure that the ethical standards and scientific merit of this study are being considered as it involves the participation of human subjects. Before the questionnaire was distributed to the participants, an informed consent letter was attached in front of the questionnaire stating the title and the purpose of the research. This included an explanation stating that answering the questionnaire is not compulsory and that at any time during the answering of the questionnaire, the participant may withdraw from participating in the said data gathering. The benefit in participating in the study is that the

participant will be informed of the result of the study and be updated on the recommendations produced by the study. The risk in participating in the study is that information will be taken from the participant who may reveal confidential information and data privacy. A Google Form questionnaire was sent to participants' email addresses due to health risks posed by COVID-19. Thereafter, data were collected after all participants answered the questionnaire.

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